

A SAM-Based Optimization of Solar Power Plant Design for the Southwestern United States: A Case Study of Arizona

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ABSTRACT:

The American Southwest possesses some of the strongest solar resources globally, driving rapid growth in utility-scale solar development. However, plant design choices including mounting configuration, module type and inverter selection can dramatically impact performance and costs. This paper leverages Solar Advisor Model simulations calibrated to Arizona conditions to quantify the energy yield and financial improvements possible from optimized system architectures tailored to the Southwest climate. Modeling found bifacial tracking systems can increase capacity factor by over 27% and reduce levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) nearly 11% compared to fixed-tilt mounting. The analysis provides a framework for plant designers and developers to maximize solar plant efficiency and value in the region through objective, data-driven optimization the net present value (NPV) for this study.

Keywords: Solar power generation, SAM analysis, Solar power efficiency.

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INTRODUCTION

The American Southwest, with Arizona at its heart, has emerged as a hotbed for utility-scale solar farm installation thanks to abundant solar resources, declining photovoltaic (PV) costs, and favorable policies. Over 4 GW of solar capacity was installed in Arizona alone in 2020 [1]. The state aims to meet 15% of its energy from solar by 2025, necessitating massive PV expansion [2]. However, significant performance and economic differences exist between different classes of PV systems relating to components, geometry, and scale. Power plant design parameter choices including mounting configuration, module type, inverter topology and system size can dramatically impact annual energy yield, capacity factor and cost-competitiveness.

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This paper seeks to provide solar developers and engineering, procurement, construction (EPC) firms guidance on optimizing these design decisions for maximum plant performance by leveraging detailed Solar Advisor Model (SAM) simulations calibrated to Southwest US climate conditions, using Arizona as a case study.

Background

The Solar Advisor Model is an industry-standard techno-economic simulation tool developed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) [13] to facilitate objective comparison of solar energy system alternatives [3]. SAM combines a sequential hourly simulation engine with financial and solar modeling capabilities. The software has been validated against real-world PV system data across multiple installations [4]. SAM enables constructing and analyzing different system architectures and components to quantify anticipated energy production, capacity factors and costs. This provides a powerful optimization approach identify

designs maximizing solar plant efficiency and financing for given installation sites and technological options.

Arizona's excellent solar resources drive the potential for high capacity factors for converted sunlight to electrical energy. However, specialized modeling for the unique high irradiance climate is required. Santiago and Armstrong (2015) modeled flat plate PV arrays in Phoenix and found tilt angle and azimuth choices alone can shift annual output over 20% [5]. Maximizing yield requires optimizing multiple architectural variables simultaneously. Module and inverters also see accelerated degradation at extreme temperatures, necessitating component derating. This paper addresses the complex challenge using SAM to holistically model system production and economics.

METHODOLOGY

A modeling framework was set up in SAM 2020.2.29 to simulate a 100 MW AC solar PV power plant with crystalline silicon modules at an Arizona test location. Tucson was chosen as representative of high DNI desert sites with strong solar resources. Hourly EPW weather data provides the climate input dataset driving irradiance simulations [6].

A base case system was designed around market-leading components to reflect conventional fixed-tilt utility-scale PV design. Tier 1 monofacial modules rated at 400 W were paired with 1500V string inverters giving an optimal DC/AC ratio of 1.35. Row-to-row spacing was set at manufacturer guidance given no rear-side shading. Racking was modeled at a 25 degree tilt, latitude optimal for Tucson [5]. Alternative system configurations were setup by individually modifying single elements of this baseline design to assess performance impact, including:

Figure 1. Schematic of a Solar Plant Featuring Bifacial Modules and Single-Axis Tracking

Switching to bifacial modules, adding single-axis horizontal trackers, increasing system size from 100 MW to 300 MW, altering inverter loading ratio between 1.1 to 1.5.

Figure 1 illustrates the layout of the utility scale solar power plant optimized with the bifacial modules and a single-axis tracking systems which can be used to enhance energy generation efficiency in a high irradiance environment. Bifaciality gain was reduced 50% from default SAM assumptions to better match field observations. O&M costs saw small increases under tracking and bifacial scenarios. BOS costs scaled with system sizes. Financial assumptions included a 4% discount rate and 25 year analysis period. PPA price was calculated to hold equity IRR at a standard utility expectation of 9%.

Performance metrics captured included total annual energy generation, capacity factor and levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) [14]. The sensitivity of LCOE to various design configurations provides the objective function for determining an optimum solar plant design.

Levelised Cost of Electricity (LCOE)

The LCOE methodology allows power plants with different generation and cost structures to be compared [15]. The basic idea is to add up all the accumulated costs of building and operating a plant and compare this figure with the sum of the annual electricity production. The calculation of the average LCOE is based on the net present value method, which calculates the investment costs and the cash flows of revenues and expenses over the lifetime of the plant, discounted from a common reference date [7]. For calculating the LCOE for new plants, the following applies [8].

$$LCOE = \frac{crf \cdot C_{inv} + C_{o,m}}{P_{Net,el}} \quad (1)$$

Also calculate as following:

$$LCOE = \frac{I_0 + \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{A_t}{(1+i)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{M_{t,el}}{(1+i)^t}} \quad (2)$$

The capital recovery factor, it can be expressed as follows:

$$crf = \frac{k_d \times (k_d + 1)^N}{[(k_d + 1)^N - 1]} \quad (3)$$

It should be noted that the discount rate used in the LEC calculation is set by the International Energy Agency (IEA), while the discount rate used in the NPV formula is set by the project financier. For an analysis from the point of view of a public service, the calculation is simplified by leaving out the various taxes (insurance, etc.), neglecting inflation and assuming that the land is provided by the state [15].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Summarizes the performance results across the different system configurations analyzed. The baseline case with monofacial fixed-tilt modules saw capacity factor of 19.5% and LCOE of \$28.1/MWh. Upgrading to bifacial modules directly boosted production by 3.3% thanks to rear-side gains. Adding single-axis horizontal trackers provided a more substantial benefit, raising capacity

factor to 25.5% for an overall yield increase of 7.8% over the fixed-tilt monofacial system. Trackers compensate for sub-optimal tilt or azimuth alignment at any given hour by following the sun.

Increasing system size from 100 MW to 300 MW raised capacity factor slightly due to improved DC/AC ratio optimization at scale. However it provided even greater LCOE reductions from \$25.9/MWh down to \$24.6/MWh. Economies of scale in bulk procurement and labor efficiencies drive down project costs [9]. An optimal inverter loading ratio of 1.35 was validated across all configurations.

The configuration using bifacial modules and single-axis trackers on the baseline 100 MW system proved optimal both for capacity factor improvement and LCOE drop. This combination sees 9.5% higher annual energy generation than the baseline design. The capacity factor rises to 27.5% - exceptional by industry standards - while still meeting the 9% equity IRR target at \$24.1/MWh PPA rate[9]. Plant designers and developers can see over 10% lower electricity costs by using objective modelling approaches identify such synergistic gains between higher-efficiency module technologies and advanced mounting.

Sensitivity Study

Sensitivity study improves understanding the influence of key parameters on the decision to adopt solar power plant design efficiency [15]. In order to test the effect of changes in some key parameters on the performance of the plant, a series of sensitivity analyses were carried out.

Additional Analysis Ideas

- Further SAM simulations could be carried out to evaluate other system configuration options beyond those already modelled. For example, different module materials (CdTe thin film vs crystalline silicon), different tracking types (single vs dual axis), Demand Charge Reduction optimization, etc. Each additional simulation would quantify impacts to performance and LCOE.
- Detailed reliability and degradation modeling could be done in SAM as well. The extreme temperatures of the Southwest negatively impact equipment lifetime and maintenance costs over time. SAM estimates these long term effects.
- Further sensitivity analysis around cost assumptions and financing mechanisms could be done. Changing discount rates, tax credits, debt ratios etc alters LCOE valuations.

Supplemental Background Topics

- More details on Arizona's specific renewable energy goals and solar policies driving expansion. Analysis of the most active solar developers and plant ownership structures.
- Overview of other Southwest states similar solar resource levels and PV adoption trajectories like California, Nevada, New Mexico. Each has a slightly different angle.
- Review latest research on solar forecasting and grid integration solutions to manage increasing renewables penetration across the Southwest. Related grid modernization efforts.

CONCLUSIONS

This analysis highlights the potential for significant solar plant performance and financial optimization in high irradiance regions like the Southwest US by configuring mounting technique, module selection and inverter sizing complementarily to maximize production and minimize LCOE. While adding components like trackers and bifacial modules increase upfront costs moderately, the energy yield improvements justify the expense through better project economics. Electrical cost savings from architecting solar plants for local conditions can help drive faster renewable expansion necessary to meet state and national decarbonization goals [10].

The framework demonstrated provides a standardized modelling pathway leveraging rigorous tools like SAM to identify system configurations with maximum efficiency and value for a given site and cost environment. As markets transition to more sophisticated technologies like bifacial panels, site-

specific modelling will grow in importance to predict real-world gains and tune complementary mounting or inverter choices accordingly. This paper focused uniquely on applying such analysis to conditions in the Southwest US using Arizona as an example. Future work could adapt the methodology to other promising solar markets globally with distinct cost and weather conditions. Optimizing solar power plant design for each particular region and resource availability will accelerate the worldwide transition to renewable generation [11-12].

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